

FORMATION OF THE SKILLS OF MIDDLE-CLASS STUDENTS "SOFT SKILLS" IN MUSIC CULTURE LESSONS

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Abstract: This article discusses the development of soft skills in middle school students in music culture classes. There is also information about the importance and effectiveness of soft skills in the education system. Soft Skills skills are also covered

Keywords: Soft skills skills, music culture, art, performance skills, interactive methods, socialization, soft skills.

The most important factor is the age-related psychological characteristics of middle-class students, the attitudes, psychological processes that appear in students during this period, the weakening of their interest in reading in this process, and the analysis of these attitudes and their correct orientation through soft skills skills cannot be exaggerated if we say that one of the highest goals in our It is necessary to first identify these attitudes in students, identify the factors that appear as a result of their age-related psychological characteristics, as well as to correctly direct them. The last ten years of research show that employers value not only professional competencies, but, as a rule, additional knowledge and skills that are not taught in universities: creativity, responsibility, politeness, etc. It is these competencies that are called "soft qualifications" – soft qualifications.

It should be noted that there is no universal definition of the term soft abilities. According to the Oxford Dictionary, "soft skills" are personal qualities that allow you to effectively and harmoniously interact with other people. We support researchers who believe that it is necessary to start from the context and field of activity in determining what soft skills are.

Speaking of the student environment, "*soft competencies*" are more formed in the extracurricular activities of students (volunteering, participation in public organizations, etc.). Soft skills-competencies that can be formed through additional education, personal experience, travel, participation in international projects, social projects. They can, of course, be used for further development in their professional activities. The skills of Soft skills have been deciphered by scientists in many stages, and we will tax this development process

Analysis of the content of the definition of "soft skills" is an important stage of our research to determine what specific skills should be formed in the process of

their professional training so that students in the future become competitive in the labor market and form effective self-sufficiency strategies in all aspects of life.

S. V. Mamaeva and V. A. Davidova believes that soft skills are mainly communication skills: the ability to conduct a conversation, ask questions, discuss one's own opinion, use feedback. A similar position is taken by D. A. Ivanov also acquires, he first of all calls soft skills communication and management skills. Based on these above skills, we can say that each student is individually stronger in some way, that is, may have a high result in some skill, but may be limping in another skill. It is usha that it is definitely not easy to identify the situation and direct it correctly, and it is advisable to take it as the most important tool to interest them through various methods of technology through music science. Another aspect of circulation is that in the secondary education system of Uzbekistan, music science is laid 1 hour a week, and it is within this hour that the development of soft skills skills in students is an important consideration. One of the most basic tasks is to determine which skills are gaining momentum in students, to develop each lesson one by one, to correctly distribute the lessons, to conduct an experiment in each of them by what method and by what technology students have, to determine each of them, and to analyze the result of the effectiveness of each skill. It's no secret that at the moment, starting from the middle class, students have a decrease in interest in classes, psychologically move away from friends, do not prepare for classes and do not take home tasks, when something has happened in their family, it is during this period that we can observe a sharp decline in mastering the lesson and a sharp In this situation, of course, a big task for us educators is to bring out of this psychological dipression in the student, as well as to increase interest in classes. This treatment, in which each subject teacher as well as the class depends on the leader, also plays a major role in music science. It is in music science that only students can listen to music, sing music, dance if they need rhythmic movement, from this state can distance the reader.

But even in this process, it is clear that there will be a student who will not listen to anything and will not join the lesson, and in this process we will need our technology for developing soft skills skills skills. We can often observe that middle-class students receive all the information very quickly despite being relatively small in age, and it is very important to take into account that they are much smaller than the upper-class student and have just moved from the primary to the middle class. At this age, it is one of our most basic psychological

tasks not to hit the student in the first place, not to punish him with an assessment, but rather to increase the student's interest in the lesson and to get it back through the soft skills skill.

In conclusion, an individual approach to each student is definitely complicated, and it is impossible to do this in 40-45 minutes. But first of all, it is one of the priority processes in which students are endowed with the ability and how to draw up technologies for their development, correctly distribute them to classes.

References:

1. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev “new Uzbekistan development strategy” publishing house “Uzbekistan” Tashkent – page 2022/19
2. SH.M.Mirziyoyev - "decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan" - PF-60 2022y
3. SH.M.Mirziyoyev-resolution of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 112 “on additional measures for further development in the field of Culture and art” 2022y.
4. Howard Gardner-“five types of intelligence that will lead to success in life” 2015y;

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